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***The impact of Algerian oil price shocks on inflation rates and the
Algerian dinar exchange rate***

أثر صدمات أسعار النفط الجزائرية على معدلات التضخم وسعر صرف الدينار الجزائري

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Abstract:

This manuscript investigates the effects of Saharan Blend petroleum price fluctuations on Algeria's economy from April 2019 to December 2023, amidst disruptions like global health crisis and the battle in Ukraine. It employs two MTNARDL models: the first explores the effect of petroleum prices on the currency rate, while the second analyzes the consequences of variations in petroleum price on inflation using the Customer Price Index. The results reveal non-normal distributions in the time series data, significant structural breaks, and a unidirectional causal relationship between Saharan Blend petroleum price and the currency rate. Notably, petroleum prices also play a crucial role in influencing inflation as well. The findings highlight Algeria's economic fragility due to its reliance on oil revenues and stress the necessity for diversification to mitigate vulnerability to external shocks. Recommendations include developing alternative sectors to enhance economic resilience.

Keywords: Algeria's economy; Global Disruptions; Causal Relationship; MTNARDL models.

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INTRODUCTION:

The COVID-19 epidemic and OPEC disputes exacerbated volatility in the worldwide oil market, resulting in substantial economic losses for nations that produce oil. Nevertheless, the implementation of extensive immunisation campaigns and the expansion of the world economy resulted in a consistent and gradual recuperation. The Ukraine conflict and Western sanctions on Russia caused significant disruptions in the global energy market, resulting in an increase in prices. Algeria saw consistent economic expansion over this time frame, but there was a significant increase in inflation, reaching 9.7% in 2023 (document, 2023). The Algerian economy relies predominantly on the exportation of oil and natural gas, rendering it susceptible to fluctuations in oil prices. These alterations affect inflation, production costs, consumer prices, and currency values. Research undertaken by (Turki et al., 2022) , (Rubia, 2022), (Gong, Chang, Chen, & Zhong, 2023) and (Simona, 2024), have shown that these shocks had an adverse impact on macroeconomic indicators in countries engaged in both oil import and export.

1. Problematic

The study addresses the challenge of Algeria's heavy reliance on oil revenues and how fluctuations in petroleum price affect Algeria's economic stability. Specifically, it examines the relationship between Saharan Blend petroleum price changes, currency rate, and inflation in Algeria over the period from April 2019 to December 2023. The central problem understands how varying levels of oil price changes impact Algeria's currency stability and inflation rates, and what this implies for the broader economic resilience of the country.

2. Hypothesis

- Increases or decreases in oil prices substantially affect inflation in Algeria, with moderate and substantial changes in petroleum prices leading to notable increases in the customer price index (CPI).
- Despite some improvements in currency stability during 2021–2022, the Algerian Dinar has not achieved full stability, and oil price volatility continues to pose a threat to economic stability.

3. Methodology

- **Granger's Nonlinear Causality Analysis:** This statistical technique is employed to ascertain the directional causation between petroleum price, currency rate, and inflation in Algeria. It allows the study to identify whether

changes in petroleum price are leading to changes in currency rate and inflation or vice versa.

- **MTNARDL (Multi-threshold NARDL) Model:**

This econometric model is employed to analyze the impact of different levels of petroleum price variations on Algeria's currency rates and inflation. The MTNARDL model is particularly useful for capturing the nonlinear and asymmetric effects of petroleum price fluctuations on macroeconomic indicators.

4. Tools Used

- **Data Sources:** Time-series data on Saharan Blend petroleum price, currency rate, and the customer price index (CPI) from April 2019 to December 2023.
- **Econometric Software:** Software like Eviews, R is used for implementing the Granger causality tests and the MTNARDL model.

I- Literature review:

Many scholars in the economic literature have thoroughly analysed the interrelation between petroleum prices and currency rates. Recent research, undertaken by (Opeoluwa & al., 2022), investigated the relationship between oil price variations and the pace of economic growth from 1981 to 2020. It used Brent oil prices as a standard and suggested that oil-producing emerging economies should give priority to the development of indigenous products and reduce imports. According to a report by (Umoru & al., 2023), the COVID-19 epidemic caused the currency to lose value and led to unstable oil prices in the economy of the WAMZ. The analysis showed that all economies in the region had a limited response to shocks, resulting in negative effects on output growth. Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Ghana, and The Gambia had a decrease in their economic growth rates as a result of a 1% depreciation of their currencies and a shock in oil prices. In a study conducted by (Joscha & Vipin, 2020), found a strong and statistically significant long-term connection between the oil price and currency rate. Thus, in the specific context of Saudi Arabia, a nation that relies significantly on oil production, any alteration in global oil demand will inevitably impact the country's currency exchange rate. (Madouri., Mekideche 2022) and (Hadda & Rym, 2024) discovered that the response of currency rates to petroleum shocks displayed asymmetric fluctuation. In research done by (Phouphet & al., 2023), found a negative spillover effects and a significant risk to Thailand's foreign currency market, especially during times of increased instability. In a study conducted by (Zaghum., Bossman 2023), an analysis of daily data from 1996 to 2022 revealed that the magnitudes of shocks had a substantial influence on the overall returns and interconnection of volatility across the system. More precisely, shocks occurring the extreme ends of the distribution have a greater impact. As to the findings of (Nasir & al., 2023), there is a significant and positive correlation between the price of oil and the exchange rate. The dataset revealed structural breakpoints occurring in February and March 2022, where stock price returns and G7 foreign currency rates were notably impacted by oil prices. The study conducted by (Bagchi., Paul 2023) examined structural fractures using the fractionally integrated GARCH model and the breakpoint unit root test. The findings demonstrate substantial and enduring impacts on memory related to oil prices, stock price returns, and foreign currency rates.

Numerous studies have explored the complex connection between oil prices and inflation. (Moosa, 1993) discovered that there is no lasting correlation between oil prices and macroeconomic indicators. (Kelesbayev & al., 2022) discovered that there

are more noticeable immediate imbalances between the oil price and inflation when the oil price declines. Russia, China, and South Africa see significant imbalances in supply, but demand and risk fluctuations have minimal effects. (Anderl., 2022) conducted a study to examine the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on the pricing of products and services in five nations, both with and without inflation targeting. The study conducted by (Suleiman & al., 2023) revealed that inflation was more strongly influenced by rises in oil prices than by reductions. study of (Shusheng & al., 2023) suggested that policymakers may employ exchange rates as a tool to effectively control inflation. The study conducted by (Belloumi & al., 2023) found that changes in crude oil prices have an asymmetric impacts on the rate of economic development, with price rises leading to greater growth rates and price drops resulting in lower inflation. The research recommends that Saudi authorities should adopt measures to address inflationary concerns. (Zhenyu., Yang 2024) indicated that positive oil supply shocks result in a reduction in inflation, but negative demand shocks lead to an increase in inflation. (Richard & al., 2024) undertook a research to examine how both global and domestic oil prices affect the inflation rate of Côte d'Ivoire. The results suggested that a higher oil price causes an increase in inflation, with a more noticeable impact shown in the context of domestic oil pricing. The analysis highlights that both Brent and fuel prices exert an equivalent and proportional impact on inflation. These data further substantiate the non-linear relationship between the variables. Linear models are ineffective for analysing data over extended time periods.

II-Methodology:

To investigate the enduring correlation between factors, we employed advanced versions of the ARDL model Multi-Threshold NARDL models which are proposed by (Verheyen, 2013) and (Debdatta., Subrata., 2016). These models allowed us to find both immediate and persistent effects within the framework.

This study utilizes indicator saturation tests to identify structural breakdowns and detect multiple breaks.

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model can be defined as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \beta + \psi_1 y_{t-1} + \psi_2 x_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \alpha_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q-1} \rho_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \rightarrow (1)$$

The dependent variable is designated as y , the vector of independent variables is represented by x , the series of differences is marked as Δ . the short run is symbolized by α_i and the long-run estimators are represented by and ψ_1 , ψ_2 can evaluate the co-integration connection using the (Pesaran., 2001) bounds test. This test employs the Fisher-statistic to examine the null hypothesis of no co-integration (Suleiman & al., 2023), especially $H_0: \psi_1 = \psi_2 = 0$. The results produce two essential values: a minimum value and a maximum value. Given the limitations, if the Fisher-statistic value exceeds the upper bound, we have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Suleiman & al., 2023). However, if Fisher-statistic is beneath the inferior bound, we accept the null hypothesis of no co-integration. However, however, we cannot ascertain the existence of a co-integration relationship if the Fisher-statistic value for the bound test is within the range set by the upper and lower bound values.

The Multiple Threshold Nonlinear ARDL (MTNARDL) method is a more advanced version of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method. It uses more than one threshold point to look for nonlinearity in the relationships between variables. This approach offers greater flexibility and a nuanced understanding of data distribution changes, particularly in cases of non-linearity. MTNARDL is a valuable

tool for econometric analysis, revealing hidden nonlinearities and enhancing data dynamics.

The two-threshold NARDL model (Debdatta., Subrata., 2016) is utilised and the Saharan blend price series (lsba) partitioned into quantiles using three partial sum series.

The user's input consists of the numbers 3, 4, 5 enclosed in parentheses.

The series of Saharan blend price (lsba) will be partitioned into subunits. $Q(\tau|\Delta lsba)$ is defined as the τ quantile of $\Delta lsba$. To compute the portion of the lower semi-bounded area (lsba) that is below the quantile, use the following formula:

$$lsba_t = lsba_t^- + lsba_t^{\bar{}} + lsba_t^+ \rightarrow (2)$$

$$lsba_t^{Q(\tau_1)} = lsba_t^- = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta lsba_j^- = \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta lsba_i I\{\Delta lsba_i < \tau_1\} \rightarrow (3) ,$$

$$lsba_t^{Q(\tau_2)} = lsba_t^{\bar{}} = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta lsba_j^{\bar{}} = \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta lsba_i I\{\tau_1 \leq \Delta lsba_i \leq \tau_2\} \rightarrow (4)$$

$$lsba_t^{Q(\tau_3)} = lsba_t^+ = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta lsba_j^+ = \sum_{i=1}^t \Delta lsba_i I\{\Delta lsba_i > \tau_2\} \rightarrow (5)$$

Where:

t : denotes the sum of observations.

$\Delta lsba_t$: Represents the first difference in lsba at time t .

The symbol $(\tau|\Delta lsba)$ represents the τ quantile of $\Delta lsba$, which acts as the threshold.

The indicator function, represented as $(\cdot)$ is valued at 1 when the condition within the parentheses is true and 0 when it is false.

$lsba_t$: symbolizes the amount of lsba at a given time.

The long-term correlation between currency rates and lsba shocks can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta laex_t = & \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 laex_{t-1} + \alpha_2 lsba_{t-1}^{Q(\tau_1)} + \alpha_3 lsba_{t-1}^{Q(\tau_2)} + \alpha_4 lsba_{t-1}^{Q(\tau_3)} \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \theta_{1j} \Delta laex_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{l-1} \theta_{2j} \Delta lsba_{t-j}^{Q(\tau_1)} + \sum_{j=0}^m \theta_{3j} \Delta lsba_{t-j}^{Q(\tau_2)} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^n \theta_{4j} \Delta lsba_{t-j}^{Q(\tau_3)} + \sum \delta_{idum} I_{it} + \varepsilon_t \rightarrow (6) \end{aligned}$$

The long-term association between the consumer price index and lsba shocks can be characterized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta lcpit = & \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 lcpit_{t-1} + \alpha_2 lsba_{t-1}^{Q(\tau_1)} + \alpha_3 lsba_{t-1}^{Q(\tau_2)} + \alpha_4 lsba_{t-1}^{Q(\tau_3)} \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \theta_{1j} \Delta lcpit_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{l-1} \theta_{2j} \Delta lsba_{t-j}^{Q(\tau_1)} + \sum_{j=0}^m \theta_{3j} \Delta lsba_{t-j}^{Q(\tau_2)} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^n \theta_{4j} \Delta lsba_{t-j}^{Q(\tau_3)} + \sum \delta_{idum} I_{it} + \varepsilon_t \rightarrow (7) \end{aligned}$$

In addition, we employ the indicator saturation technique to uncover any anomalies and detect any significant changes in the structure. The software was developed by (Søren., Bent., 2008).

Include dummy or indicator variables in the list of predetermined regressors.

This study entails estimating the first bivariate analysis equation, which examines the effect of Saharan Blend petroleum price on Algerian's currency rate. Conversely, the second equation investigates how petroleum Saharan Blend price shocks influence inflation through the customer price index. We represent these equations as (6) and (7), respectively.

Laex, and Lcpi denote the Algerian currency rate, small oil shocks (-), medium oil shocks ($\pm$), high oil shocks (+) and the customer price index, respectively. We represent the fixed term and estimation parameters in long time. the short-run estimation coefficients, the outlier indicators, and their respective coefficients. At time t, an outlier is defined as 1 during that specific period and 0 for all other periods. Each equation is associated with its respective white noise.

III-Data and Stochastic Properties:

This article uses monthly statistics from April 2019 to December 2023. The sample period spans from 2019 to 2023 and includes notable disruptions caused by the 2020 health crisis and the battle in Ukraine.

Model1: A simplified model that considers the lsba determines laex. This model is based on the works of (Peter & al., 2003). The model assumes a small and open economy that relies on the production of two distinct categories of commodities: those intended for oil exports, as demonstrated by Algeria, and non-tradeable items.

$$Laex=f(Lsba)$$

Model2: Oil is a commodity that has had past instances of sudden and significant changes in price. Oil plays a vital role in the manufacturing process of several companies, and it might pose challenges for these companies to shift away from its usage in an abrupt surge in price. Petroleum price shocks can have significant and wide-ranging repercussions on the economy, including the potential for inflation. When there is an abrupt and significant raise in the petroleum price, companies that depend on petroleum for their production will have to increase their prices in order to safeguard their profits, or else they may lose a portion of their earnings. The phenomenon of enterprises passing on an increase in production costs to consumers through increased pricing is referred to as the cost pass-through effect. The inflation rate in an economy can be affected by a petroleum price shock due to the cost pass-through effect. To integrate the influence of petroleum price variations on inflation (Richard & al., 2024), the price of petroleum will be included in the expectation-augmented The Phillips curve in equation form.

The Consumer Price Index, or CPI, is defined by the (U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics) as "a measure of the average change over time in the prices paid by urban consumers for a market basket of consumer goods and services."

The CPI is presently the most scrutinized measure of inflation. Oil prices have long been known to track the CPI. A spike in oil prices can raise the cost of consumer commodities because manufacturers must account to offset their escalating manufacturing and transportation costs. Naturally, the expenses are passed on to their customers.

$$Lcpi=f(Lsba).$$

The Figure 1 illustrates that the kernel density function distributions of the analysed time series differ from the theoretical distribution. They are not normal and have distortions. The lsba and the lcpic have high points in their tail distributions, whereas the exchange rate does not exhibit kurtosis because it has multiple high points.

Fig1: kernel density distribution of data

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program.

Table 1 presents the stochastic and statistical characteristics, indicating that all series show departures from normality, as demonstrated by the kernel density distribution and the Jarque-Bera statistic measures. This demonstrates the unpredictable nature of these series and influences the selection of approaches employed in the investigation. All series exhibit departures of the normal distributions, exhibiting both onto the left and to the left skewness, indicating their symmetrical tendencies. To be more specific, lsba is positioned at the extreme left end of the distribution, while the laex and lcpi are located at the far right. The kurtosis of oil prices surpasses the benchmark value of 3, suggesting a distribution that is leptokurtic. The BDS test for nonlinearity in Table 2 confirms the presence of these characteristics across many embedding dimensions. This implies that the data is heterogeneous. The inherent unpredictability of this behavior underscores the importance of employing non-linear models and non-linear Granger causality approaches in this research (Opeoluwa et al., 2023).

Table1 : Descriptive-statistics

	laex	lsba	lcpi
Skewness	0.127318	-1.290442	0.343570
Kurtosis	1.936408	5.382687	1.685425
Jarque-Bera	6.200661	29.30313	6.225639
Probability	0.04446	0.000000	0.040028

Table 2 BDS test

dimensions	2	3	4	5
lsba	(0.157785) <0.011711> [13.4736] {0.0000}	(0.257188) < 0.01886 > [13.6368] {0.0000}	(0.31688) <0.02276> [13.9208] {0.0000}	(0.345423) < 0.02405> [14.36152] {0.0000}
Laex	(0.151017) <0.005782> [26.12038] {0.0000}	(0.246327) <0.009302> [26.4799] {0.0000}	(0.306723) <0.01121> [27.36274] {0.0000}	(0.339468) <0.011821> [28.71628] {0.0000}

lcp	(0.1862) <0.00602 > [30.8901] {0.0000}	(0.314016) <0.0096 > [32.70869] {0.0000}	(0.400637) <0.01145> [34.98454] {0.0000}	(0.41014) <0.011955> [38.56135] {0.0000}
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(.) : $BDS_{statistic}$, <. >:Standard error, [.]: Z-statistic, {.}: Probability.

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program

IV-EMPIRICAL RESULTS:

IV-1- Detecting structural breaks: The saturation indicators test, presented in Table 3, verified the presence of structural fractures

Table 3: Test results for Outliers Indicator Saturation

Outliers Indicator Saturation		
Model: Change in Step-shift and Trend		Number of obs=57
Lags=0		Maximum lags = 0
		Date
	laex	lcp
Step-shift(SIS)	2022M09***	2021M08*** 2022M04*** 2023M03***
TRENDBR(TIS)	2020M02*** 2020M04*** 2020M05*** 2020M11***	

***: Significant interpretation at 1% probability.

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program

IV-2- Unit Root Test:

The stationarity of the variables considered in this study was assessed individually by conducting an Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) developed by (George & Yongcheol, 2006) unit root test. Which results for the variables are showed in Table 4.

Table 4: Stationary Test

	levels			first difference		
	laex	lsba	lcp	laex	lsba	lcp
Constant	-0.648	-2.231	0.434	-5.058***	-6.32***	-5.68***
Constant and trend	-1.362	-3.049	-2.948	-5.485***	-6.26***	-6.13***
None	0.475	-0.097	3.067	-5.037***	-6.38***	-6.02***
	levels			first difference		
	$lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}$	$lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}$	$lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}$	$lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}$	$lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}$	$lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}$
Constant	-1.801	-1.608	-1.315	-4.979***	-7.21***	-4.62***
Constant and trend	-2.553	-2.774	-1.859	-5.159***	-7.405***	-4.71***
None	0.474	0.395	0.878	-4.472***	-6.502***	-3.92***

***: Significant interpretation at 1% probability.

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program

Upon examination of Table 4, it is observed that the variables *lsba*, *laex*, and *lcpi* are stationary at the first difference because the test statistic values exceed the table values in absolute terms. Also the three regimes of $(lsba_t^{Q(\tau_1)}, lsba_t^{Q(\tau_2)}, lsba_t^{Q(\tau_3)})$ are stationary at the first difference.

IV-3- Causality Test Results

Table 5 displays the findings of a brief term linear Granger causality examination with the VAR framework. In the full dataset, the findings indicate that there is a unidirectional linear causal connection between *lsba* and *laex* alone.

The conventional linear causal relationship may not yield adequate results due to its failure to account for the inherent asymmetric correlations in time series. In the next step, we will look into how regime shifts or structural fractures can change the outcomes of the linear Granger test. We will also consider the possibility that the relationship between *lsba*, *laex*, and *lcpi* might not be linear.

Table 5: Linear Test

H ₀ :	Obs	F-Statistique	Prob
<i>lsba</i> → <i>laex</i>	55	5.00852**	0.0104
<i>laex</i> → <i>lsba</i>	55	0.2289 ^{no}	0.7962
<i>lsba</i> → <i>lcpi</i>	55	0.31 ^{no}	0.73
<i>lcpi</i> → <i>lsba</i>	55	2.02 ^{no}	0.14

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program

Previous studies (Yudong., Chongfeng, 2012), have confirmed the presence of a non-linear pattern in oil prices. Hence, we conduct an analysis of the non-linear structure of our sample data and investigate the non-linear correlation between *lsba* and *laex*, as well as *lcpi*. We utilize feed-forward neural networks, as recommended by (Youssef , 2020).

A non-linear Granger causality test identifies intricate correlations between variables that linear models may neglect. It facilitates the identification of causation in non-linear interactions, providing enhanced insight into dynamic systems, particularly within economic frameworks. Upon analysing table 6, the non-linear Granger causality test reveals that *lsba* is the primary factor influencing the fluctuations in the *laex* and *lcpi* in Algeria with a 99% and 95% degree of confidence respectively. There is no established causal link between the currency rate, inflation, and oil prices in Algeria.

Table 6: Non-Linear Granger Causality Test

Pairwise NlinST Sample : 2019M04- 2023M012 Lag :3				
H ₀ :	Obs	GCI	F-Statistique	Prob
<i>lsba</i> does not Granger Cause <i>laex</i>	54	0.188227	7.66299***	0.0087
<i>laex</i> does not Granger Cause <i>lsba</i>	54	0	-0.09	1
<i>lsba</i> does not Granger Cause <i>lcpi</i>	54	0.374606	2.72651**	0.0274
<i>lcpi</i> does not Granger Cause <i>lsba</i>	54	0	0.393	0.972

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the R program

IV-4- MTNARDL Estimation:

We are fascinated by the possibility of fluctuating oil prices having an effect on both laex and lcpi. Therefore, we set the benchmarks for oil prices at 25% and 75%.

25% Threshold: Determine the precise value that aligns with the data's 25th percentile after sorting it in ascending order. This figure represents the 25th percentile of the lsba distribution, demonstrating that 25% of the prices are below it and 75% are above it.

75% Threshold: Determine the value that, when sorted in ascending order, corresponds to the data's 75th percentile. This figure represents the 75th percentile of the lsba distribution, showing that 75% of the prices are below this value and 25% are above it.

The Figure 2 illustrates the three regimes $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_1)}$, $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_2)}$, $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_3)}$.

Figure2: graphic representation of the three regimes of lsba

Source: Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program

The results of the Wald statistical test of model 1 and model 2 indicate, as shown in Table 7, that there is an asymmetric short-term trend in lsba, while in the long term there is a symmetric trend. As for the bounds testing, its results showed that there was a co-integration between the Laex variable and the independent variables $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_1)}$, $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_2)}$, $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_3)}$, also between Lcpi variable and the independent variables $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_1)}$, $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_2)}$, $lsba_t^{Q(\tau_3)}$ the 1% level, indicating a long-term relationship. The estimations results for the error correction model 1 and model 2 showed that the MTNARDL error correction parameters is negative (-0.731737), (-0.442641) respectively which means their absolute value are less than 1. It has a negative signal that is statistically significant at the 1% level and a probability ratio of zero.

Over the long duration (according to model 1), small changes in lsba have an adverse impact on laex, suggesting that even modest movements might destabilise the currency. Nevertheless, moderate and substantial fluctuations in lsba exert no meaningful influence on the currency laex.

In the long time (according to model 2), medium and large lsba shocks have a considerable beneficial influence on lcpi. Nevertheless, minor fluctuations in oil prices have relatively little effect on lcpi.

Table 7 displays the results from the MTNARDL model. Our investigation reveals that the MTNARDL estimations are stable, as demonstrated by the cumulative

sums and their squares tests. The MTNARDL technique has been characterized by its robustness and validity.

Table 7: Results of the MTNARDL model estimation

Variables	Model 1(laex)	variables	Model 2 (lcpi)
Long run estimation		Long run estimation	
$lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}(-1)$	-0.16607***	$lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}$	0.018249 ^{no}
$lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-1)$	0.296958 ^{no}	$lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-1)$	0.30079**
$lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}(-1)$	0.076129 ^{no}	$lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}(-1)$	0.048504***
c	4.539976***	c	5.045512***
Short run estimation		Short run estimation	
Cointeg [*]	-0.731737***	Cointeg [*]	-0.442641***
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}$	-0.009327 ^{no}	$\Delta lcpi(-1)$	0.017674***
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}(-1)$	0.070149***	$\Delta lcpi(-2)$	-0.118446 ^{no}
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}(-2)$	0.06639**	$\Delta lcpi(-3)$	-0.418262**
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}(-3)$	0.083411***	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}$	0.047178 ^{no}
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}(-4)$	0.059919***	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-1)$	-0.131098*
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_1)}(-5)$	0.049148***	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-2)$	-132752**
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}$	-0.003044 ^{no}	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-3)$	-0.065847 ^{no}
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-1)$	-0.180389***	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}$	0.020135 ^{no}
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_2)}(-2)$	-0.054641***	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}(-1)$	-0.004372 ^{no}
$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}$	0.013983 ^{no}	$\Delta lsba^{Q(\tau_3)}(-2)$	-0.0329**
@after ("2022m09")	0.027929***	@after ("2021m08")	0.009006 ^{no}
@after ("2020m02")	-0.037107***	@after ("2022m04")	0.01894**
@after ("2020m11")	0.034903***	@after ("2023m03")	0.026542***
c	4.539976***	c	2.2333***
Bound test	7.80192***	Bound test	6.352**
WSR	3.66**	WSR	1.769*
WLR	-	WLR	-
LM-test	3.476	LM-test	1.766
ARCH	0.1724	ARCH	0.325
Cu sum	S	Cu sum	S
Cu sum Square	S	Cu sum Square	S

Significant levels at 1%, 5%, and 10% are denoted by the symbols ***, **, and *, respectively. Prepared by the researchers using FMI data and using the Eviews13 program.

IV-5- Discussion:

The results of the nonlinear Granger causality analysis reveal a unidirectional nonlinear causal relationship in Algeria between *lsba*, the *laex*, and *lcpi*. This relationship indicates that variations in *lsba* directly influence these economic variables in a complex and nonlinear manner.

IV-5-1- MTNARDL Model Findings

The MTNARDL model provides further insights into this dynamic:

- **Exchange Rate:** Small variations in oil prices negatively affect the *laex*, indicating that even minor fluctuations can destabilize the currency. However, medium and major *lsba* shocks do not significantly impact the *laex*, indicating that even minor fluctuations can destabilize the currency.

However, medium and major *lsba* shocks do not significantly impact *laex*. This suggests that

the currency is more sensitive to smaller, frequent Changes rather than larger, sporadic ones.

- **Consumer Price Index (CPI):** Medium- and large-scale fluctuations in lsba have a significant effect on the lcp_i, with significance values of 5% and 1%, respectively. This highlights that substantial changes in lsba directly impact consumer prices, this phenomenon is ascribed to inflation driven by cost-wherein escalating oil prices result in heightened production and transportation expenses, which are then transferred to consumers. Comparable outcomes were observed in (Akhil Sharma, Abdul Rishad, & Sanjeev Gupta, 2019).

IV-5-2 Short-term Imbalances

The analysis demonstrates an inherent imbalance in the short-term link among petroleum prices, currency rate, and the customer index of price. Although the currency saw some improvement following the rise in oil prices in 2021 and 2022, it was insufficient to achieve complete stability because the persistent volatility in these economic indicators. The study reveals several key insights into how inflation (cpi), currency rate, and petroleum prices are related in Algeria during the period from April 2019 to December 2023:

1. **Causal Relationship:** The Granger nonlinear causality analysis confirms a one-way causal link from petroleum price to both currency rates and inflation in Algeria. This indicates that variations in petroleum price are a principal factor influencing alterations in the currency rate and inflation rates in Algeria.
2. **Impact on Exchange Rates and Inflation:** The MTNARDL model demonstrates that while minor fluctuations in Saharan oil prices have an adverse effect on exchange rates, moderate and substantial changes significantly influence the consumer price index (CPI), leading to increased inflation.
3. **Currency Stability:** Despite some improvements in currency stability observed during 2021–2022, the Algerian Dinar has not achieved full stability, indicating that the economy continues to be susceptible to Saharan Blend petroleum price shocks.

This underscores the fragility of Algeria's economy and its over-reliance on oil revenues.

IV-5-3- Need for Economic Diversification

The economic challenges Algeria faced during this period highlight the critical need for economic diversification. Reducing dependence on oil revenues is essential to mitigate the risks associated with oil price volatility and to strengthen financial stability. Diversifying into other sectors such as renewable energy, agriculture, and technology could provide a more stable economic base and reduce the economy's susceptibility to external shocks.

V-Conclusion

V-1- Test of Hypotheses

- (Impact on Inflation): The hypothesis that fluctuations in oil prices significantly impact inflation is also supported. The MTNARDL model shows that moderate and substantial the CPI is significantly impacted by variations in petroleum price. Confirming that petroleum price volatility contributes to inflation.

- **(Currency Stability):** The hypothesis that the Algerian Dinar has not attained full stability despite improvements is confirmed. The findings indicate that the currency remains sensitive to oil price fluctuations, highlighting ongoing economic vulnerabilities.

Overall, this research offers a thorough comprehension understanding of the complex interrelations involving petroleum price, currency rate, and inflation in Algeria. The findings highlight the urgent need for strategic economic reforms to build a more resilient and diversified economy, ensuring long-term financial stability and sustainable growth

V-2- Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations can be made to policymakers in Algeria:

1. **Economic Diversification:** Algeria should prioritize diversifying its economy to reduce reliance on oil revenues. Developing other sectors, such as manufacturing, agriculture, and renewable energy, could help stabilize the economy and reduce vulnerability to oil price fluctuations.
2. **Stabilizing Exchange Rates:** Implementing policies aimed at stabilizing the exchange rate is crucial. This could include enhancing foreign exchange reserves, improving monetary policy frameworks, and exploring hedging strategies against oil price volatility.
3. **Inflation Management:** To better manage inflation, the government could consider tightening fiscal policies and improving the efficiency of public spending. In addition, implementing focused subsidies and price restrictions on necessary commodities might assist in reducing the effects of inflation on disadvantaged groups.
4. **Strengthening Financial Sector:** Strengthening the financial sector through improved regulation, increased financial inclusion, and the development of capital markets can provide a buffer against external shocks and enhance overall economic stability.

These recommendations aim to support Algeria in achieving greater economic resilience and stability, reducing the country's dependence on oil, and ensuring more sustainable growth.

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People's Democratic Republic of Algeria
Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research
University Centre of Maghnia. Algeria
Institute of Economics, Commercial Sciences and Management

THE PROGRAM OF
'1ST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ECONOMICS,
BUSINESS & FINANCE”
2&3 JUNE, 2024

DAY ONE : SUNDAY, JUNE 2, 2024

Venue : Center of Andalusian studies. Tlemcen

Zoom link:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/82013389702?pwd=XBEMVjj2hbJLW6hhfKiUKY2CSaxBu.1>

Zoom Meetings Room ID: 820 1338 9702

Password: 229695

THE OPENING SESSION: 9 H - 10 H

Quran Verses

Anthem National Algerian

Welcome speech from:

Pr. Naoum Mourad, Director of University Centre of Maghnia

Pr. Chibi Abderrahim, Conference Chair

Pr. BENBOUZIANE Mohamed, Chairman of the scientific committee

Mr. Youcef Bechlaoui, the WALI of Tlemcen

PLENARY SESSION: 10 H- 12.30 H

Moderators: Pr. BENBOUZIANE Mohamed		
Auditorium	KEYNOTE SPEAKERS	
10:00 - 10:45	Prof. Rabah Arezki <u>Harvard Kennedy School. USA</u> <i>"Africa's Shifting Economic Paradigm"</i>	
10:45 - 11:30	Prof. Amir Lebdioui <u>Oxford Department of International Development. UK</u> <i>"Survival of the Greanest: Economic Transformation in a Climate-Conscious World"</i>	
11:30 - 12:00	Debate	
12:00 - 12:30	Coffee Break	

WORKSHOP "A": 13H - 15H15**Moderators: Prof. Derbal Abdelkader**

Room A	Energy Studies		
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
13h - 13h15	Renewable Energies in Oil-producing Countries: A Transition or an Addition? A wavelet-based analysis -Case of Algeria-	Mohamed Benbouziane Hadjer Boulila Ilham Benaissa	Abou Baker Belkaid University. Tlemcen
13h15 - 13h30	The Effect of Climate Legislation and Regulation on ESG firms considering CEO's role	Kamel Si Mohammed	University of Ain Temouchent, Algeria
13h30 - 13h45	Achieving the environmental sustainability through the renewable energies: Green Hydrogen, Solar, and Wind energy as a pillar	Benazza Hanaa	University of Tlemcen, MECAS research laboratory
13h45 - 14h	The green transition implications for energy security: The Net-Zero Emissions (NZE) Scenario (2050)	Amira ALLOUIT Abdelwafi BOULOUIZ Hamida KHALDI	Djilali Bounaama University University Center of Naama
14h - 14h15	Spatial Panel Data Analysis of Sustainability, Energy and Economic Growth in 31 Selected Developing Countries	Salaheddine SARI-HASSOUN Ahmed BOURICH Meryem Nabila Hachim	University Centre of Maghnia
14h15 - 14h30	Study of educational mismatch in the Algerian labor market Using probit regression model	Maamari Fatma LAASASI MOUNDIR	National Higher School of Statistics and Applied Economics ENSSEA) Research Center in Applied Economics for Development CREAD
14h30 - 14h45	Islamic Finance as a Catalyst for Financial Inclusion: Empirical Evidence from Panel Logit Models in OIC Countries	Achouak BENKADDOUR Ahmed HALALI Lila AYAD Mohammed BALKHIR	University of Tamanghasset Algeria Ahmed Draia University Algeria
14h45 - 15h15	Debate		
15h30	Lunch		

WORKSHOP "B": 13H - 15H15**Moderators: Prof. Benhabib Abderrezak**

Room B	Economics, Management, Marketing		
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
13h - 13h15	Natural Language Processing (NLP) Analysis of the Bank of Algeria's Communiqués	Hacene Tchoketch Kebir Abderazak Madouri	Research Center for Applied Economics for Development (CREAD)
13h15 - 13h30	Financial inclusion, Natural resource rent, and Economic growth: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa	Abderazak MADOURI Chemseddine TIDJANI	Research Center for Applied Economics for Development (CREAD)
13h30 - 13h45	Cultivating Sustainability: The Role of Agriculture in Achieving Zero Hunger and Economic growth in Algeria	Seyf Eddine Benbekhti Ahmed Zeghoudi Mohammed Bouknadil	Tlemcen University
13h45 - 14h	How using derivative instruments affects capital market risk of GCC commercial banks?	BENDIMA Nesrine ZEDDOUN Djamel	Tlemcen University Ain Temouchent University
14h - 14h15	The contribution of international auditing standards to strengthening corporate governance requirements	CHOUIREFI Hadjer	University of SIDI BEL ABBES DJILLALI LIABES
14h15 - 14h30	Sales Automation from Lead Acquisition Stage to Closing Deals: A Case Study of Yves Rocher.	HAMDOUNE ASMA	University, Sidi Bel Abbes Algeria
14h30 - 14h45	Mapping the Scientometric Landscape: Trends and Themes in Artificial Intelligence and Marketing Research	FRIOUI Samira GRAA Amel	University of Djillali Liabes, Sidi Bel Abbes
14h45 - 15h15	Debate		
15h30	Lunch		

WORKSHOP "C": 13H - 15H15**Moderators: Prof. Chibi Abderrahim**

Room C	Financial Economics		
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
13h - 13h15	Public governance and Foreign Direct Investment in Algeria "Analytical Applied Study"	Daoudi Mohammed Mennad Merwa	University Centre of Maghnia
13h15 - 13h30	The impact of Algerian oil price shocks on inflation rates and the Algerian dinar exchange rate	Madouri Hadda Bouchelit Rym	University Centre of Maghnia
13h30 - 13h45	Unveiling the Future of Labour Productivity in Algerian Agriculture	Mohammed Fouad Gassem	University Centre of Maghnia
13h45 - 14h	Impact of Financial Stability on Economic Growth in Algeria, 1990-2022.	FILALI Youcef OTMANI Faiza	Oran Graduate School of Economics University Centre of Maghnia
14h - 14h15	Financial Openness, Economic Growth And Policies For Financial Strability: Empirical Evidence	Zenasni Soumia	Tlemcen Higher School of Management, Algeria
14h15 - 14h30	A Study on the Efficiency of Conflict Early Warning Systems in Managing Conflicts at Business Organizations	Moaredj Houari Riadh Kadri	University of Ghardaia (Algeria) University Centre of Maghnia
14h30 - 14h45	Credit risk in Algerian public banks and informational opacity. Field survey	Fatima Zohra Marouf Zeyneb Guellil	Umons, Waroqué, Belgium, Tlemcen University Faculty of Economics, Algeria,
14h45 - 15h	Algorithmic Herd Behavior (AHB) of High-Frequency Trading (HFT): Is it more effect by deep learning machine on financial market stability than human's	Hichem Gharbi	El Oued University
15h - 15h15	Debate		
15h30	Lunch		

DAY TWO: MONDAY, JUNE 3, 2024

Zoom link:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/82812740479?pwd=tpyIyKKgnWupoZ2HO6zyYtqHtVGzQH.1>

Zoom Meetings Room ID: 828 1274 0479

Password: 099824

PLENARY SESSION

Moderators: Prof. Amir Lebdioui			
Discussant: Prof. Benbouziane Mohamed			
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
9h -09 h15	Recent developments in financial econometrics	Fredj JAWADI	Université de Lille , France
09 h15 – 9 h30	Frugal as the Future of Innovation	Mir Dost	The University of Winchester. UK
09 h30- 09 h45	AI's Dark Divide: The Looming Crisis of Educational Inequality	Fawad Khaleel	Edinburgh Napier University. UK
09 h45-10 h	Energy Efficiency Among Government Offices in Region Xii: A Stochastic Frontier & Data Envelopment Analysis	KATHLEEN IVY Z. BOLOTAOLO	University of Mindanao. Philippine
10 h- 10 h15	Lifelong Learning in the Age of AI: An Empirical Investigation into the Drivers of Human Capital Investment Amid Technological Change in OECD Countries	Amina Aouini Chokri abdennadher	Faculty of economics and management Sfax. TUNIS
10 h15- 10 h30	Debate		
10 h30 – 11h	Break		

WORKSHOP "A": 11 H – 14 H

Zoom link: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/82812740479?pwd=tpyIyKKgnWupoZ2HO6zyYtqHtVGzQH.1>

Zoom Meetings Room ID: 828 1274 0479

Password: 099824

Moderators of Session1: Dr. Sari Hassoun Salaheddine			
Discussant: Prof. Sahed Abdelkader			
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
11 h -11h15	Comparative analysis of dynamic stochastic general equilibrium models and agent-based models	Samira Boulahbel-Bachari	CREAD

	for economic policy evaluation		
11 h15 – 11 h30	Price Level Determination in Algeria: Analyzing Fiscal and Monetary Policies through the Lens of the Prisoner's Dilemma	Chibi abderrahim Zahaf Youcef Chekouri SidiMohammed	University Centre of Maghnia
11 h30- 11 h45	The Impact of Financial Inclusion on Bank Performance and Bank Stability: A Panel ARDL Analysis	Fatima Zohra Talhaoui Ahmed Benlaria Mohamed Mediani	University Ahmed Draia - Adrar
11 h45-12 h	Is there an Augmented nonlinear Taylor rule in Algeria? Evidence from QARDL approach	Meryem Gadiri	University Centre of Maghnia
12 h- 12 h15	External borrowing and its implications on economic growth in Tunisia An Econometric Study for the period 1990-2022	HAMMAMI Raid Imade Eddine CHABANI Amina Yousra	University of Ghardaïa University Center Nour Bachir of El Bayadh
12 h15- 12 h30	Debate		
12 h30 – 12 h45	Break		
Moderators of Session 2: Prof. Chekouri sidi Mohamed			
Discussant: Prof. Benazza Mohammed			
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
12 h 45-13 h	The Impact of Capital Adequacy according to Basel Committee Requirements on Return on assets Study a sample of Commercial Banks Using Panel Data	Farah BENSALÉM Khemissi GAIDI	University of khenchela abbes laghrour University of Bordj Bou Arreridj
13 h– 13 h15	The Role of Islamic Banks in Achieving Sustainable Development – Al Baraka Bank as a Model –	Hanane TLEMÇANI Ouieme SOUR	University of Tlemcen
13 h15- 13 h 30	The Contribution of Islamic Banking to Enhancing Financial Inclusion: A Case Study of Al Baraka Bank Algerian Branch - Chlef	Souaad Elmiloudi Fatima Fouka Djazia Hassini	Hassiba Ben Bouali University – Chlef
13 h 30-13 h 45	A Multi-Tiered Approach : Examining the Effect of Business Creation on Growth in Different MENA Economies	Abdelhadi Benghalem Anwar SEKIOU Amine Benslimane	Oran Graduate School of Economics University of Tiaret University of Oran 2
13 h 45- 14 h	Debate		
14h – 15h	Ending Sessions/Closing Ceremony		

WORKSHOP "B": 11 H – 14 H

Google Meet: <https://meet.google.com/zme-nrbq-dia>

**Moderators of Session1: Dr. Guellil Mohamed Seghir
Discussant :Prof. Mekidiche Mohammed**

TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
11 h -11h15	Study The Nonlinearity Effects of The Digital Economy on Economic Growth in Algeria	Sahed Abdelkader Bensenouci Merouane MekidicheMohammed	University Center of Maghnia
11h15 – 11h30	The Impact of Financial Inclusion on Economic Growth In High-Income Arab Countries : A Quantile Regression Approach	Benaini Rahima Selka Brahim	University Center of Maghnia
11h30- 11h45	Bank efficiency, performance, and oil price changes: a semi-parametric study in listed GCC banks	Samiya Metair	University Centre of Maghnia
11h45-12h00	Did institutional distance and financial development gap matter for BRICS+ membership? A decryption essay using Panel Threshold Regression (PTR) Approach	Reda Hamza Boudjana Samer Mehibel	CREAD
12h- 12 h15	Algeria and the BRICS: What is the most useful form of cooperation for Algeria?	Samer Mehibel Reda Hamza Boudjana	CREAD
12h15- 12 h30	Debate		
12 h30 – 12 h45	Break		
Moderators of Session 2: Dr. Ayad Hicham Discussant: Dr. Benlabed Mohamed			
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
12 h 45-13 h	Opportunities and Challenges of start-ups Financing in Africa	Narimane Benabderrahmane Hassiba ALMI	CREAD University, Annaba
13 h– 13 h15	Theoretical foundations of the new geographic and territorial economy	Souhila KIRAT Mounir LOUADJ Fatima BOUSSALEM	Jijel University
13 h15- 13 h 30	From shadows to solutions: Automatic data-driven system for Green Hydrogen stations using deep learning	Salma Hanane Yahyaoui Khadidja Berbaoui Noureddine	Mascara University

13 h 30-13 h 45	The Role of AI In Supporting and Enhancing Decision-Making Process Within Organizations	Guembour Abderraouf Louadj Mounir Raki Nadira	University of Jijel
13 h 45- 14 h	Debate		
14h – 15h	Ending Sessions/Closing Ceremony		

WORKSHOP "C": 11 H – 14 H

Google Meet: <https://meet.google.com/vxi-sahy-smk>

Moderators of Session1: Prof. Bellahcene Mohammed			
Discussant : Dr. Bouriche Ahmed			
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
11 h -11h15	Human Resources Management and Skills Development: Major Challenges for the Performance and Competitiveness of Algerian Companies	Mohammed Lazreg Abdelbassit Meddah Mounir Azouz	University of Sidi Bel Abbés University of Algiers 3 University of Bordj Bou Arreridj
11 h15 – 11 h30	The Role of Training in Human Skills Development and the Socio-Economic Sector - the case of some productive companies in the state of Tlemcen	Bessaid Oussama Nabil Saidi Tarek	Higher Business School, Tlemcen
11 h30- 11 h45	Transforming Performance Management : Integration of Artificial Intelligence into Balanced Scorecard framework - A Case Study of Siemens Company	Saadia Benahmed Miloud Benkheira Aboubakr Hansal	Relizane University Mostaganem University
11 h45-12h	Human Development Indicators in Hong Kong Study of the period 2010-2021	Feddaoui Amina	Chadli Bendjedid University, El Tarf
12 h- 12 h15	Covid-19 and Women Migrant Domestic workers(MDWs) in the Middle East, Impacts, Policies to response and Lessons Learned	Sabrina MORTET	University of Relizane
12 h15- 12 h30	Debate		
12 h30 – 12 h45	Break		
Moderators of Session 2: Prof. boudjenane tawfiq			
Discussant : Nemich khadidja			
TIME	TITLE	Authors	Affiliations
12 h 45-13 h	Exploring the Role of Web 4.0 in the Development of the Tourism Industry	Nesrine Zerrouki Mohamed Bendehiba	University of Khemis Miliana University of Tissemsilt

13 h– 13 h15	Modelling by the structural equation of the factors affecting the attitudes of Algerian tourists towards domestic tourism in Algeria	Kherouf Mounir Linda Friha Rym Touamria	University of Guelma University of Khenchela
13 h15- 13 h 30	From Perception to Action: The Impact of Switching Costs and Perceived Value on Guests Behavioral intentions in Algerian Hotels -A PLS-SEM Analysis	Zerouati Maouahib	University of Setif 1
13 h 30-13 h 45	The role of knowledge management in developing intellectual capital	kacemi Med Mounir	University of Tamanrasset
13 h 45- 14 h	Debate		
14h – 15h	Ending Sessions/Closing Ceremony		

University Centre of Maghnia. Algeria
Institut of Economics, Commercial
Sciences and Management

ACCEPTANCE LETTER

Dear honorable author,

Our pleasure is great to inform you that your paper submitted to the 1st International Conference on Economics, Business & Finance (ICEBF 2024) scheduled to be held on June 2 and 3 by the University Centre of Maghnia, has been accepted for presentation in a regular session.

The next step for you is to pay registration fees on the following account :

CCP CUMAGHIA 323585 CLE 54

Please, note that you are invited to register before **27 May 2024**, and send the payment receipt to the conference email : leppeselab@gmail.com

We invite you to prepare your slides and presentation in **English**. The presentation should not exceed 15 minutes. A discussion is expected for 5 minutes and questions /answers also for 5 minutes.

We look forward to meeting you in Center of Andalusian studies. Tlemcen.

We eagerly await your presence.

Yours sincerely,

The ICEBF 2024 organizers

University Centre of Maghnia, Algeria
Institut of Economics, Commercial
Sciences and Management

INVITATION

Dear honorable guest:

Our pleasure is great to invite you for

1st International Conference on: Economics, Business & Finance

2-3 June 2024

Venue : Center of Andalusian studies, Tlemcen

Keynote Speakers

Pr. Rabah Arezki.
Harvard Kennedy
School. USA

Pr. Amir Lebdioui
Oxford University
UK

Pr. Mohammed
Saad. Bristol
Business School.
UK

Pr. Fredj Jawadi.
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